

MODELING THE PROCESS OF SEPARATION OF COTTON PARTICLES FROM AIR IN THE WORKING CHAMBER OF A COTTON SEPARATOR

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Annotation: The article presents the results of the study of the laws of motion of cotton particles in the working chamber of the separator, located along the inlet pipe of the vacuum valve. When the change in the displacement of the cotton pieces in the horizontal and vertical directions over time was studied, it was found that the cotton pieces entering from the inlet pipe fell into the vacuum valve in about 0.4 s. From the results obtained, it can be seen that the main part of the cotton pieces falls on the front of the vacuum valve. The established laws can be used in the design of new constructions of cotton separators.

Keywords: cotton, separator, pneumatic equipment, pipe, vacuum valve, separation process, air flow.

1. Introduction: General Concepts

The cotton separator is one of the main elements of the pneumatic transport equipment, which is responsible for separating the cotton from the air flow carrying it, taking it out of the equipment and transferring it to the next process. In this direction, one of the important issues in the separator working chamber is to increase the efficiency of the equipment by maintaining its original quality and reducing process energy consumption in the process of separating the cotton piece from the air flow without damaging it.

In the existing separators, it is observed that the work efficiency is not at the required level, as a result of which the cotton pieces stick to the surface of the separator mesh. Accordingly, a separator located along the vacuum-valve inlet pipe was designed, which eliminated the existing shortcomings, which are allowed to increase dramatically the efficiency of the separator.

Figure 1 shows an improved construction scheme of the cotton separator, which includes the inlet pipe 1, the mesh surfaces on the side walls of the separation chamber 2, the shaft 3, the pulley 4, the shafts fastened to the 5 nets, the cotton suckers attached to the 6 mesh surfaces, 7 Vacuum air intake pipes, 8 Vacuum valve located perpendicular to the working chamber, 9 Vacuum valve shaft, 10 blades, 11 elastic material attached to the edge of the blades, 12 belt, 13 reducer, 14 clutch, it consists of 15 shafts and bearings mounted on shafts. This

construction is the object of study and we study the movement of cotton in this separator.

Figure 4.11. Improved design of the separator

2. Mathematical model analysis

The Cauchy problem in this case is solved numerically in the MAPLE -2020 program.

In both cases the air flow velocities $V_0 = 15 \text{ m/c}$, $V_0 = 20 \text{ m/c}$, $V_0 = 25 \text{ m/c}$ values, the corresponding motion trajectories of the cotton pieces are obtained graphically.

Figure 3a shows the trajectory of the stationary motion in the separator working chamber with the cotton pieces 1 and 2 in a horizontal position. As can be seen from the graphs, the air flow 15 c/m va 25 c/m when the range changes, it can be observed that the cotton pieces fall mainly into the first half of the vacuum valve.

This process $V_{y1}(t)$ can also be observed from the fact that the velocity assumes a zero value in the range of $0.1 \div 0.3 \text{ m}$ along the OX axis. The trajectory of the 2nd cotton piece is the same as that of the 1st cotton piece, we can observe the direction of the vacuum-valve towards the zero velocity along the OX axis at $0.3 \div 0.8 \text{ m}$, where the vertical velocity is zero at $0.2 \div 0.35 \text{ m}$.

Figure 3b shows the law of change of cotton pieces in the horizontal and vertical directions over time. As can be seen from the graph, at around 0.4 sec, the cotton pieces have time to fall into the vacuum valve.

Figure 3b shows the laws of motion of the separator working chamber in the vertical position of the cotton pieces 1 and 2. As can be seen from the graphs, the process of dropping the cotton pieces into the vacuum valve is observed to be a bit slower over time than in the horizontal position, but it can be seen that they fall more into the front of the vacuum valve.

Calculation of the productivity of cotton balls, the work of falling into the vacuum-valve socket:

$$m_0 = m_1 + m_2 = 0,4 + 0,45 = 0,85z \text{ weight}$$

$$t_0 = 0,25 \text{ sec drop speed}$$

$$t_1 = 1 \text{ sec } m_1 = 3,4zp$$

$$t_2 = 60 \text{ sec } t_2 = 60$$

$$t_3 = 1 \text{ hour } m_3 = 12240zp$$

Taking into account the entrance surface to the working chamber of the separator, in the working chamber, it is possible to separate 19,584 tons of cotton per hour from the air.

In addition, the speed of the cotton pieces in the horizontal direction is several times smaller than the speed of sliding it, the speed in the vertical direction is reduced to zero, reducing their impact on the back of the separator, completely reducing the cases of sticking to the mesh surface.

1 – 0,22 m $V_0 = 15 \text{ m/c}$;

2 – 0,4 m $V_0 = 20 \text{ m/c}$;

3a-figure

3b-figure

4. Conclusion

1. The study of the laws of motion of cotton particles in the working chamber of the separator, where the inlet pipe is located along the vacuum valve, showed that the cotton pieces entering the inlet hole fall into the vacuum valve after about 0.4 s.

2. The main part of the weight of the cotton is removed through the primary part of the vacuum valve of the separator in accordance with the law.

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